

The Influence of Functional Values, Emotional Values, and Social Values Mediated by Attitudes towards Purchase Intentions of Halal Products in E-Commerce Online Sales

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Abstract:- The increase in the intention to buy halal products is becoming increasingly massive with the existence of E-Commerce. Through the Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (SEM-PLS) method, it can be seen which variables influence directly, indirectly or through mediation, the intention to buy halal products. The research uses primary data with a total sample of 200 respondents. The results of this study prove that by mediating attitudes, functional values influence purchase intentions and social values directly influence purchase intentions. While emotional value has no significant positive effect on purchase intention and attitude.

Keywords: Component; Halal Products; Functional Values; Emotional Values; Attitude, E-Commerce.

I. INTRODUCTION

Halal products in Indonesia have developed rapidly and become a trend in all sectors. Not only in the halal food sector but also in the pharmaceutical, cosmetic, lifestyle and tourism sectors. Based on the report of the State of Islamic Economy Report (DinarStandard, 2022) Indonesia's halal food sector is ranked 1st in the world, which is up three levels from the previous year. Likewise, the halal cosmetics and recreational media sector is ranked 2nd with consumption reaching USD 4.7 billion for cosmetics and USD 22.4 billion for recreational media. Then followed by the pharmaceutical sector which is ranked 4th in the world with a large consumption reaching 5.4 billion USD. All the increase in consumption in these sectors has made Indonesia ranked 4th in the world as a world consumer of halal products.

The consumption of halal products that continues to increase has several factors with the biggest influence coming from religious commitment and the internet. The factor of religious commitment for the Indonesian population with a majority Muslim community makes awareness of the consumption of halal products higher. This has been proven through empirical studies such as research by Nurul Huda, et al (2018) religious commitment has the highest level of significance to the consumption of halal

products. So are the results research by Ihsana, Hakim and Sulistyono (2021) that the religious factor still has the most important influence on the consumption of halal products among the people of Banda Aceh.

The next factor is the internet which is one of the technologies to facilitate shopping and broad access. This is evidenced by an increase in the spending value of the Indonesian population of USD 282 billion in 2022 in the halal industry sector which previously only reached USD 184 billion in 2020 (katadata, 2022).

In addition, with today's digital technology, people use information and communication to buy and/or sell goods and/or services via the internet, which is known as E-Commerce or online sales. Data shows that in 2022 many E-Commerce (Marketplace) platforms will increase and compete between E-Commerce (Marketplace). Some of the best-selling product categories in online sales according to the Indonesian Digital Marketing Association include beauty products, home appliances, Muslim fashion, women's clothing, mobile phones and accessories, health, women's bags, mother and baby, electronics, men's clothing and food and beverages (Indonesian Digital Marketing Association, 2022).

The consumption behavior has been carried out by the Indonesian population regarding halal products can also be referred to as purchase intention because it is based on various factors that can motivate consumers to buy (Ho and Wu, 2012). Halal certification for a product also has a function in increasing the selling value of the product in the eyes of consumers (Zuhri, 2020).

Purchase intention in general has many factors that influence it as in research (Suparno, 2020) uses the hedonism variable, utilitarianism (epistemic value) as a research variable in shopping motivation. Suparno (2020) uses the Stimuli Organism Reaction (SOR) approach to empirically prove that hedonism values, utilitarian values, and religiosity have a positive effect on purchase intentions (purchasing). intention) on halal products. Then research Sangroya and Nayak (2017) adopted the GPV to investigate the factors that influence the buying behavior of green

energy consumers emphasizing developing a multidimensional construct of the GPV and examining the components of the GPV such as functional value, emotional value and social value for further in-depth research.

According to Zulmi Ramdani (2020) research problems with too many sources and too large a population can be overcome by conducting an initial study or pre-survey.

Based on the studies previously mentioned, the variables that can influence purchase intention consist of Hedonism, Utilitarianism, Functional Value, Social Value, Emotional Value, Behavior and Epistemic Value. While the respondents used were 30 E-commerce users based on sampling standards for variables that totaled more than two (Ramdani, 2020).

Table 1 Pre-Survey Results

Variable	Yes	Not
Hedonism	15	15
Functional value	28	2
Epistemic Value	21	9
Emotional Value	25	5
Social Value	23	7
Behavior	25	5
utilitarian	18	12

From the seven variables tested in the pre-survey, it was found that four variables had the highest scores, namely Social Value, Functional Value, Emotional Value and Behavior. Therefore, this research will be continued with social value, functional value and emotional value variables as independent variables mediated by behavioral variables.

II. LITERATURE REVIEWS

➤ *Stimulus-Organism-Response (SOR) Theory:*

This theory originally came from psychology, which later became a theory in communication (Effendi, 2003). The principle of this theory is the response which is the back reaction of the individual when receiving a stimulus from the media. One can expect or predict an effect link between mass media messages and audience reactions, it can also be said that the effect is a special reaction to the response stimulus, so one can expect and estimate the suitability between the message and the communicant's reaction.

This theory is a basic development of the Stimulus - Response (SOR) model with the basic assumption that the mass media has a directed, immediate and direct effect on the communicant. SOR theory is mostly used exclusively in the context of on-site shopping activities. This study takes from the internal motivational model the hedonic, utilitarian, and perceived value shopping values (babindkk., 1994;McKinney, 2004 ;O'Brien, 2010) and several previous studies on halal products (AbdRahmandkk., 2015; Aisyah, 2017).

➤ *Perceived Value Theory*

Perceived value is the consumer's overall assessment of the usefulness of a product (or service) which consists of several values that influence the product selection process (Kotler and Keller, 2009). According to (Tjiptono, 2014) Perceived Value can be measured by the following assessments:

- Functional value, according to Sweeney and Soutar (2001) functional value is a condition when customers feel the expectation of an item in accordance with what they get. Functional character and practical thinking that can control can regulate when making decisions in buying useful products, in conditions that are too self-focused or self-oriented are very prominent.
- Emotional value, related to feelings (Surachman, 2008). Emotional value is often associated with product aesthetics (eg, religion). Based on this explanation, it can be concluded that Emotional Value is a consumer's assessment of the ability of a product or service to give affective feelings.
- Social value, namely the perception of utility obtained from product associations with one or more certain social groups. Social Value is measured on the selected image profile. Choices that involve highly visible aspects of the product (e.g. clothing, jewelry) or goods and services that may be shared with others (e.g. gifts, products used in entertainment) are often driven by social values.

➤ *Attitude Theory*

One's intention to buy a product/service is influenced by one's attitude towards buying behavior and subjective norms. This is in line with opinion by Ajzen (2008) who say that the intention to behave can be known by estimating attitudes towards behavior and subjective norms, where a person's actions are the realization of a person's desire or intention to act (Sigit, 2006).

Behavioral mediation of purchase intention can be seen from previous studies. Consumer intention to buy organic foods is predicted by attitudes toward them (Tarkiainen and Sundqvist, 2005; Gracia and de Magistris, 2007; Lodorfos and Dennis, 2008). Research by Tarkiainen and Sundqvist (2005) Michaelidou and Hassan, (2008) also indicates that a positive relationship between the two exists in the literature.

According to Chen and Barnes (2007), purchase intention has the meaning that is a condition when consumers want to make or intend to make purchases online.

There are several stages to purchasing a product online, the first is by searching for the product you want to buy, the second is by transferring information about the product we are looking for, and the third is buying the product online (Pavlou, 2003). Purchase intention is defined as the consumer's opportunity to purchase a product (Sam & Tahir, 2009).

➤ *Purchasing Online Theory*

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➤ *Halal Product*

Halal is a term in Islam that comes from Arabic. Halal means "permitted" or permissible (Ihsana et al, 2021). According to Qardhawi (2007) in Ihsana et al (2021), etymologically halal means things that are permissible and can be done as long as there is no shari'a argument against it. While the product is defined as something that is made or produced to be traded in order to fulfill consumer needs (Thamrin & Tantri, 2012).

The Law of the Republic of Indonesia since 1945 has mandated that the state will guarantee the independence of each of its residents to embrace their religion and beliefs, including the obligation to provide protection and guarantees regarding the halal products consumed and used by the public (UU 1945 Articles 20 & 21). Law Number 33 of 2014 has explained in detail regarding halal products. Halal products are products that have been declared halal in accordance with Islamic law in general, the products referred to are goods or services related to food, drinks, medicines,

cosmetics, chemical products, biological products, genetic engineering products, as well as goods that can be used or utilized by Public (Copy of Law No 33, 2014).

➤ *E-Commerce*

Online shopping is a process in which consumers directly buy goods, services and others from a seller interactively through internet channels (Indrajaya, 2016). One of the internet channels that can be used to shop online is E-Commerce. E-Commerce is an online channel that can be reached by someone through an electronic system. Usually, this online channel is used by businesses to make sales and is used by consumers to obtain information about goods or services that can meet their needs (Kotler & Armstrong, 2012). According to Jony Wong, the definition of E-Commerce is electronic commerce in the form of buying, selling, and marketing of goods and services through electronic systems (Binus, 2020)

III. RESEARCH AND METHODOLOGY

➤ *Type and Source of Data*

The data source in this study uses primary data obtained using a questionnaire data collection method. The type of data in this study uses the Partial Least Square (PLS) based Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) approach. PLS is an alternative model of covariance based SEM. PLS is used to confirm a theory by looking at the relationship between several variables and determining how good the theory is. In addition, PLS is also to develop theory in exploratory research by explaining the variance in the dependent variable when examining the model (Hair et al., 2017).

➤ *Population and Sample*

The population in this study is very broad because it is aimed at all people who use E-Commerce to buy halal products. Therefore, the technique of determining the sample in this study uses a purposive sampling technique, so in this case the researcher determines the sample, namely:

Table 2 Sample Criteria

Characteristics	Categories
Age	18 – 24 years
Application	Have e-commerce (shopee, tokopedia, bukalapak, etc.)
Religion	Islam (Muslims)

In this study, the sample size can be calculated using the number of independent variables = 4 with a significance level = 5% and a minimum R² = 0.25, so that the sample size obtained is 37 respondents with each comparison group (high education and low education). According to (Hair et al., 2017) the sample size obtained can also be calculated using Gpower 3.1 software with parameter error = 5%, statistical power = 95% and the number of predictors = 4 (Erdfelder et al., 2009).

Fig 1 Gpower Sample Sampling Measurement

Based on the calculation of Figure 1 above, the total sample size obtained is 129 people. To obtain greater statistical power, the number of questionnaires to be distributed is 200 respondents.

➤ *Technique and Data Analysis*

The statistical analysis technique used is Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). PLS-SEM analysis was chosen because it can test latent variables regardless of normality and sample size problems (Chin et al., 2008). In general, analysis with PLS-SEM requires two stages sequentially, namely the measurement model and the structural model (Dean et al., 2019). In the measurement model, the analysis focuses on evaluating the reliability and validity.

The data analysis technique in this study used the PLS technique which was carried out in 2 stages. The first stage was to test the measurement model (outer model), which tested the construct validity and reliability of each indicator. The second stage is to test the structural model (inner model) which aims to determine whether there is an influence between the variables/relations between the constructs as measured using the t test of the PLS itself. The specifications for the PLS model in this study were created using the SmartPLS 3.2.9 for Windows software. The following discusses each step of the SEM analysis using SmartPLS.

IV. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS OF RESEARCH

➤ *Result of Measurement Model Test (Outer Model)*

This Outer Model test will define how each indicator has a relationship with its latent variable, and in this Outer Model the tests carried out include; Convergent Validity, Discriminant Validity, Composite Reliability, Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Cronbach Alpha.

• *Convergent Validity*

Test the validity of the Convergent indicator seen from the value of the loading factor for each construct. Research that is confirmatory, the recommended loading factor value is 0.7 and greater than 0.7.

Meanwhile, for exploratory research, the loading factor value is still acceptable, ranging from 0.6 to 0.7 and the average variance extracted (AVE) value must be greater than 0.5 (Hair et al., 2017). The value of composite reliability in confirmatory research must be greater than 0.7. Meanwhile, for exploratory research, the composite reliability value is still acceptable if it is still worth 0.6 to 0.7 (Hair et al., 2017). The following is the Outer Model result which shows the Outer Loading value using Smart PLS 3.

Table 3 Factor Loading, Cronbach Alpha, CR, AVE

Variable	Indicator	Outer Loading	Cut off Value	AVE	α	CR	Ket.
Functional Value	NFS1	0.860	0.70	0.678	0.881	0.913	Valid
	NFS2	0.845	0.70				Valid
	NFS3	0.807	0.70				Valid
	NFS4	0.842	0.70				Valid
	NFS5	0.759	0.70				Valid
Emotional Value	NEMS1	0.895	0.70	0.678	0.842	0.893	Valid
	NEMS2	0.890	0.70				Valid
	NEMS3	0.709	0.70				Valid
	NEMS4	0.785	0.70				Valid
Social Value	NSOS1	0.831	0.70	0.714	0.868	0.909	Valid
	NSOS2	0.864	0.70				Valid
	NSOS3	0.828	0.70				Valid
	NSOS4	0.857	0.70				Valid
Value (Behavior)	SKP1	0.850	0.70	0.698	0.855	0.902	Valid
	SKP2	0.788	0.70				Valid
	SKP3	0.890	0.70				Valid
	SKP4	0.809	0.70				Valid
Purchase Intention	NB1	0.781	0.70	0.631	0.802	0.871	Valid
	NB2	0.870	0.70				Valid
	NB3	0.837	0.70				Valid
	NB4	0.758	0.70				Valid

The test results based on table 1.4 above show that the Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability results for each variable value are above the minimum value of 0.70, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each variable value is above the minimum value of 0.50 and Outer Loading respectively variables above the minimum value of 0.70. In other words, all the constructs or research variables have become fit measuring instruments, and all the questions used to measure each construct have good reliability, so the indicators for each construct meet the convergent validity criteria.

• *Discriminant Validity*

Discriminant Validity is the Fornell Larcker Criterion, which is a method that compares the square root value of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of each construct with the correlation between other constructs in the model (Henseler, J., et al 2016). A construct is said to be valid by comparing the root value of AVE (Fornell-Larcker Criterion) with the correlation value between latent variables. And for the HTMT value in each construct it is less than 0.9, which means that each variable has its own meaning, because Henseler et al (2016).

Table 4 Discriminant Test

Validity Fornell-Larcker					
Variable	NB	NEMS	NFS	NSOS	SKP
PI	0.794				
EMSV	0.624	0.823			
FSV	0.596	0.766	0.823		
SOSV	0.623	0.722	0.587	0.845	
ATD	0.612	0.592	0.691	0.429	0.835
HTMT Validity					
Variable	NB	NEMS	NFS	NSOS	SKP
PI					
EMSV	0.734				
FSV	0.699	0.868			
SOSV	0.743	0.837	0.652		
ATD	0.719	0.664	0.788	0.481	

Based on the Fornell-Larcker test table and the HTMT test in each of the above categories, it can be concluded that the square root of the average variance extracted (AVE) for each construct is greater than the correlation between one construct and the other constructs in the model. From the AVE and HTMT values, the constructs in the estimated model fulfill the discriminant validity criteria.

• *Collinearity*

This test is done by looking at the value of VIF (Variance inflation factor). The variance inflation factor(VIF) is the square root (VIF) which is the rate at which the standard error (alpha). Based on the table below, all categories show that the VIF value of each indicator is less than 5.

Table 5 VIF Value

Connection	Score
EMSV→PI	3,395
FSV→PI	3,092
SOSV→PI	2.103
ATD→PI	1,952
EMSV→ATD	3,335
FSV→ATD	2,438
SOSV→ATD	2.101

• *Fit Test*

Table 6 Fit Summary

Parameter	Score
SRMR	0.075
NFIs	0.921
RMStheta	0.112

Based on the table below, the SRMR value is less than 0.08 from the three categories. In addition, RMStheta is a threshold value (conservative), for each RMStheta is less than 0.12. While NFI is a measure of the suitability of the model on a comparative basis against the baseline or null model, each value is greater than 0.90.

• *Coefficient of Determination R-Square (R2)*

This analysis is also to determine the goodness of the structural equation model. The greater the R-square number indicates the greater the independent variable can explain the dependent variable so that the structural equation is better. According to Sarstedt. M, (2019), an R-Square value of 0.75 is strong, while a value of 0.50 is moderate, and 0.25 is weak. Based on the data processing that has been done, the R-Square value is obtained as follows:

Table 7 R-Square Test Results (R2)

Variable	R Square
Purchase Intention (Y)	0.543
Attitude (Z)	0.488

Based on the R-Square value in Table 7, it shows that the R-Square value of the Purchase Intention variable (Y) is 0.543. This value means that the variability of the construct of Purchase Intentions can be explained by the variability of the Attitude construct of 54.3%. This value indicates a "moderate" relationship category, while the remaining 45.7% is explained by other variables outside the one studied.

Meanwhile the R-Square value of the Attitude variable (Z) is 0.488. The R-Square value which shows the simultaneous effect of Functional Value, Emotional Value, and Social Value on Attitude (Attitude) of 48.8% indicates a "moderate" relationship category, while the remaining 51.2% is explained by other variables outside those studied.

• *Predictive Relevance Test Q-Square (Q2)*

A Q2 value that is greater than 0 (zero) indicates that a model has predictive relevance, and conversely a Q2 that is smaller than 0 (zero) indicates that a model has less predictive relevance (Ghozali & Latan, 2015). The results of the Q2 test can be seen in the following table:

Table 8 Predictive Relevance (Q²)

Variable	SSO	SSE	Q ²
PI	848	569,365	0.33
ATD	848	581,846	0.31

Based on the results of the Construct Cross Validation Communality Test in table 8 above, it can be seen that all variables have a value greater than 0. Thus it can be interpreted that all variables have a very strong value, where the highest number is with a value of Q2 = 0.329 meaning that the variable Purchase intent has strong predictive value and is relevant.

• *F Square Test (F)*

F-Square (effect size) is a measure used to assess the relative impact of an influencing variable (exogenous) on the affected variable (endogenous). This equation formula is used to find out whether the endogenous latent variable is significantly affected by the exogenous latent variable.

Table 9 F-Square Test Results (F2)

Connection	F2	EffectSize
Emotional Value →Purchase Intention	0.009	Small
Functional Value →Purchase Intention	0.002	Small
Social Value → PurchaseIntention	0.131	Currently
Attitude → PurchaseIntention	0.140	Currently

Based on the category table above, the F2 value on the relationship between Emotional Value and Purchase Intention is 0.009, which means it has a small effect size, the F2 value on the relationship between Functional Value and Purchase Intention is 0.002, which means it has a small effect size, while the relationship between Value Social with purchase intention has an F2 value of 0.131, which means it has a moderate effect size. In addition, in the relationship between attitude and purchase intention, the F2 value is 0.140, which means it has a moderate effect size.

• *Path Coefficients*

Hypothesis testing is done by looking at the path coefficients which show the parameter coefficients and the significance value of the t-statistic. The influence between variables is declared significant if it has a t- statistic value greater than the t-table or has a P value <0.05. Meanwhile, testing the mediating effect uses the procedure developed by Baron and Kenny (Ghozali and Latan, 2015) where the effect of exogenous variables on the mediating variable must be significant at the t-statistic > 1.96.

Table 10 Test Path Coefficients

Variable	Path Coefficients	P Values
	(β)	
Emotional Value ->Purchase Intention	0.119	0.286
Emotional Value ->Attitude	0.175	0.169
Functional Value ->Purchase Intention (Purchase Intention)	0.052	0.594
Indigo: Functional -> Attitude	0.579	0.000
Social Value -> Purchase Intention (Purchase Intention)	0.355	0.000
Indigo:i Social -> Attitude	-0.037	0.609
Attitude -> PurchaseIntention (Purchase Intention)	0.353	0.000

➤ *Results of Hypothesis Testing and Mediation*

Based on the test results, if the path coefficient is positive, P Value < 0.05 and T Statistics > 1.96, the hypothesis is accepted and it is concluded that exogenous variables have a positive effect on endogenous variables. The results of data processing are as follows:

Table 11 Hypothesis Testing Results

Hypothesis	Path Coefficients (β)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values	Information	Mediation
FSV -> ATD	0.579	0.106	5,47	0.000	Be accepted	-
EMSV -> ATD	0.175	0.127	1.377	0.169	Rejected	-
SOSV -> ATD	-0.037	0.072	0.512	0.609	Rejected	-
FSV -> PI	0.257	0.091	2,808	0.005	Be accepted	-
EMSV -> PI	0.181	0.094	1,913	0.056	Rejected	-
SOSV -> PI	0.342	0.078	4,397	0.000	Be accepted	-
ATD -> PI	0.353	0.084	4,19	0.000	Be accepted	-
FSV -> ATD -> PI	0.205	0.058	3,543	0.000	Be accepted	Partial Mediation
EMSV -> ATD -> PI	0.062	0.051	1.217	0.224	Rejected	Non Mediation
SOSV -> ATD -> PI	-0.013	0.026	0.493	0.622	Rejected	Non Mediation

- *Based on the Table above, the Results can be Obtained:*
- ✓ Based on the hypothesis testing in this study, the results of the Statistical T value were 5.470; P Value 0.000; and the original sample value of 0.579. The T statistic value is more than 1.96 and the original sample value shows a positive value. This result shows that the functional value has a positive and significant effect on attitude (behavior).
- ✓ Based on the hypothesis testing in this study, the results of the Statistical T value were 1.377; P Value 0.169; and the original sample value of 0.175. The T statistic value is less than 1.96 and the original sample value shows a positive value. This result shows that emotional value has no negative and insignificant effect on attitude.
- ✓ Based on the hypothesis testing in this study, the results of the Statistical T value were 0.512; P Value 0.609; and the original sample value is -0.037. The T statistic value is less than 1.96 and the original sample value shows a negative value. This result shows that social values have a negative and insignificant effect on attitudes.
- ✓ Based on the hypothesis testing in this study, the results of the Statistical T value were 2.808; P Value 0.005; and the original sample value of 0.257. The T statistic value is more than 1.96 and the original sample value shows a positive value, this result indicates that the Functional Value has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intentions.
- ✓ Based on the hypothesis testing in this study, the results of the Statistical T value were 1.931; P Value 0.056; and the original sample value of 0.181. The T statistic value is less than 1.96 and the original sample value shows a positive value. This result shows that emotional value has no negative and insignificant effect on purchase intention.
- ✓ Based on the hypothesis testing in this study, the results of the Statistical T value were 4.397; P Value 0.000; and the original sample value of 0.342. The T statistic value is more than 1.96 and the original sample value shows a positive value, this result shows that Social Value has a positive and significant effect on Purchase Intentions.
- ✓ Based on the hypothesis testing in this study, the results of the Statistical T value were 4.190; P Value 0.000; and the original sample value of 0.353. The T statistic value is more than 1.96 and the original sample value shows a positive value, this result shows that attitude (behavior) has a positive and significant effect on purchase intention.
- ✓ Based on the mediation hypothesis test in this study, it is known that Attitude (Behavior) mediates the relationship between Functional Value and Purchase Intention to purchase online (E-Commerce). This is based on the indirect effect test which obtained a P Value of 0.000 or less than 0.05.
- ✓ Based on the mediation hypothesis test in this study, it is known that attitude (behavior) does not mediate the relationship between Emotional Value and Purchase Intention (Purchase Intention) on online purchases (E-Commerce). This is based on the indirect effect test which obtained a P Value of 0.224 or more than 0.05.
- ✓ Based on the mediation hypothesis test in this study, it is

known that attitude (behavior) does not mediate the relationship between Social Value and Purchase Intention (Purchase Intention) on online purchases (E-Commerce). This is based on the indirect effect test which obtained a P Value of 0.622 or more than 0.05.

V. CONCLUSION

- *Based on the Results and Discussions Carried Out in this Study, It Can be Concluded that:*
- Functional Value positive and significant effect on attitude (Attitude)
- Emotional Value negative and not significant effect on Attitude (Attitude).
- Social Value negative and not significant effect on Attitude (Attitude).
- Functional Value positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention.
- Emotional Value positive and insignificant effect on Purchase Intention.
- Social Value positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention.
- Attitude positive and significant effect on Purchase Intention.
- Attitude mediate the relationship between Functional Value and Purchase Intention (Purchase Intention) on online purchases (E-Commerce).
- Attitude does not mediate the relationship between Emotional Value and Purchase Intention (Purchase Intention) on online purchases (E-Commerce).
- Attitude does not mediate the relationship between Social Value and Purchase Intention (Purchase Intention) on online purchases (E-Commerce).

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